

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

TEACHING THE USE OF "MACROS" IN APPLICATION PROGRAMS

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Abstract

This article dedicated to learning how to create effective software systems using all the capabilities of the Algorithmic Language.

Keywords: Macros, Visul Basic, Customize Ribbon, Options, Developer, Record Macros Methods.

Macros are a tool that eases the user's work by repeating any action repeatedly on any page with one touch. Macros are implemented in all applications.

Purpose: Although macros are implemented in all applications, macros are most often used in the Microsoft Excel application. It is possible to save n number of operations performed by any created button in a macro and repeat it as many times as necessary. Despite the fact that macros have such a feature, this section of Excel is not properly taught in high school or higher education schools.

Macros are used in two ways:

The 1st method is to open macros on any page of the pushed application program and perform the steps, then we go to the code part of Visul Basic and see the VBA language of the completed steps within the module.

Method 2: Add a module from the Insert menu in Visul Basic. we create macros by activating the code line of the created module in the project window and referring to the desired page.

In order to work with macros in Ms Word, you need to do some work in the ribbon header of Ms Word first. For the average user, this ribbon title is not very important. But since we're dealing with macros and lines of code, we need to debug the tape header. Open the file menu and activate the "OPTIONS" sub-category from the opened window, activate "CUSTOMIZE

RIBBON" from the opened window. From the window that opens on the right side, in the "CUSTOMIZE the RIBBON" window, activate the check mark in front of the "DEVELOPER" ribbon title and press the OK button. When we reload the Microsoft Word application, we will see the title "DEVELOPER" in the ribbon header.

Now we can work with macros:

Or to get wet with macros

1. From the VIEW ribbon title MACROS then RECORD MACROS or 2. From the DEVELOPER ribbon title MACROS then RECORD MACROS

Now let's create a macro using any method

For this, we have to plan what we want to do in advance, that is, we have to prepare a technical project. For example, we often want to apply to the management of the company we work for any work, and we have to write an application for this. For this work, we prepare an "Application" form in a macro, and if necessary, use this form with a button.

If we click the cursor on RECORD MACROS

Such a window will open, change the name of the macro to "Application" and click the cursor on the "Button" and the Custommize true quick access toolbar window will open. From this window, name the macro "Application" and click OK. It is necessary to use the letters of the English alphabet.

Now we prepare the desired document and stop the macro. The button of the template document we prepared is ready in the quick request panel. After that, we can place these macros in the desired document on our computer in one step

Figure 1

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Bashirova Goncha I. by her daughter

Application

So our new macro is ready and its icon appears in the quick access panel. We can prepare as many such macros and use them in any MS Word document. To

know which macro is there, if we place the cursor under the macros, we read its name. Let's create a new macro, for example: "Student Registration"

Youth Union of the Republic of Azerbaijan

Name _____

Surname _____

Date of birth _____

Graduated from _____

Date:00/00/2000

Signature _____

Figure 2

We can create a macro by using hot keys. For example, by pressing the "Ctrl+G" key, we can create a macro and use it in the desired document. If we press the cursor on the "Keyboard", then it asks us to select the hot key. So, if we press the Hot key on the desired page, we need macro will appear.

Now let's work with macros in Ms Excel..

1 VIEW ribbon heading MACROS then RECORD MACROS

2 From the DEVELOPER ribbon heading MACROS then RECORD MACROS

Now let's create a macro using any method.

For this, we must plan what we want to do in advance, that is, we must prepare a technical project

Let's say that it is necessary to collect information about some of the students studying in universities and send them to training in any department.

We plan what to do on any sheet of the Excel workbook, for example Sheet1

Sheet3 page where we will place the table, and return to Sheet1 and create our macro

Figure 3

Our macro's usual Tableau shortcut is Ctrl+c

Figure 4

In this macro, we copied the information about the student, moved it to Sheet3 and placed it in the table in a horizontal position, then made all the letters Bold, then Italic font size 14, and the background yellow

fonts red. Let's go back to Sheet1 and clear the table so that we can write information about the next student. Let's do all these steps with one button.

Figure 5

After we create this macro, we need to store it in a different memory so that we can use it when we need it. If we save it as an Excel workbook, then we will

Figure 6

lose our macros. In order to save the macros without losing them, from the window that opens File-Save as, name our macro in the Save as type section Excel Macro Enabled Workbook and save it in memory. To make our work even easier, let's close this macro to a

button. . Therefore, we select a button from the Developer Insert Form Controls section, draw a rectangle with the " + " sign obtained on the Excel page, and rename it as we want.

Now let's create that button.

Figure 7

That is, from now on we will perform up to n operations by pressing one button.

Now let's look at the Visual Basic section in Developer to see the Visual Basic (VBA) code of all these steps we did.

That is, when macros are active, all the steps we do are written in the form of program codes.

Figure 8

Macros, one of the most important features of MS Access, are a collection of certain commands. To create a macro, we click on the Macro constructor and first select the object type of the macro, the object type can be a query, a form, a report, or even both or all three. After recording this, we give the macro a name, record the type, and save, so the macro is created. Macros help us do the work that we would solve with a few buttons and functions with just one click.

Macros also provide a convenient user interface for database management. Sometimes a macro itself consists of multiple macros. In this case, which macro will be executed at what time is regulated with the help of conditional statements. Macros in Access are called

in two ways: - through the user's command (with the help of the appropriate form in the menu); - with the help of any system event (when the form is opened or closed). Sometimes, when opening a database, a condition for automatic execution of a number of actions appears. A special macro called Autoexec is used for this.

To set up macros, a macro command is selected and the corresponding parameters are set. After organizing the macro, it can be executed from the database window. A macro can also be associated with a button. In this case, the macro is executed when the key is pressed. To create a macro, select Macros→Create mode from the database window.

To create a macro, the Constructor window opens, by pressing the button, the required macro command is selected from the list of macro commands. In the lower part of the window, the blank corresponding to the selected macro command - Argument macro command is marked.

When working with macros, the following must be taken into account:

User-written macros remember user "mistakes" and under certain circumstances these "mistakes" can be exposed. For this reason, macros should be tested under different conditions.

Before writing a macro, the user should prepare a well-thought-out command script. The universality and optimality of the macro should be emphasized in this command scenari Macros with multiple commands are more likely to have "multiple" errors.

Macros can become "intellectual" only after appropriate changes are made in the VB editor.

It is strictly forbidden for a user without the necessary knowledge of VBA programming to modify unprotected macros or procedures/functions. Because "instead of making eyebrows, they can remove eyes"

I think that if informatics teachers spend some time teaching macros while teaching applied software, they can make students interested in the programming profession.

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